

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B032
 Date: 20 Jul 2004
 Take Off: 10:00:11
 Landing: 15:32:30
 Flight Time: 5h32m19

Trials Instructions: ITOP – Interception and characterisation of N American pollution
Operating Area: N and W of the Azores

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Reeves	UEA
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	York University
7	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
8	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
9	WAS-PAN	Lisa Whalley	Leeds University
10	PERCA	Alex Parker	Leicester University
11	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
12	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
13	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
14	Mission Scientist 2	Paul Monks	Reading University
15	Observer	Peter Cook	Cambridge University
16	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
17			
18			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B032
 Date: 20th July 2004
 Project: ITOP
 Location: Horta, Azores

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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100011		T/O	0.0 kft	089	
100421	100719	Run 1	5.0 kft	091	
101000					SATCOM call to M. Smith
101243	101355	Run	12.9 - 13.9 kft	074	paul1
101411	101701	Profile 1	14.1 - 17.0 kft	072	
101801					PSAP flow on
101848	110303	Run 2	17.0 kft	072	
103405					JW cal. complete
103908		EVM	17.0 kft	047	Paul 2
104252		EVM	17.0 kft	047	Claire 1
104641		EVM	17.0 kft	040	CO 600 ppb
110433	110721	Profile 2	17.0 - 19.5 kft	261	
110822	111506	Run 3	19.4 kft	276	
111000					SATCOM call CCM to DFL
111521	112052	Profile 2	19.4 - 24.0 kft	274	restart
112216	112721	Run 4	24.0 kft	274	
112721	113127	Profile 3	24.0 - 20.4 kft	275	
113127	113644	Run 5	20.4 kft		
113644	114108	restart Profile 3	20.5 - 16.2 kft	273	
113925					TWC off, on
114030					TWC heater 2 on, off
114308	114527	restart Profile 3	16.3 - 14.0 kft	081	
114527	115009	Run 6	14.0 kft	087	
115009	120030	Profile 3.1	14.0 - 17.0 kft		
115009					HORACE crash
120030	124718	Run 7	17.0 kft	275	
122755		EVM	17.0 kft	265	CO ppb >500
124200		EVM	17.0 kft	262	Co ppb >500 again
124839	130800	Run 8	17.0 - 20.9 kft	337	
124956					HORACE crash
130500					HORACE crash
130934	131910	Profile 4	21.2 - 26.0 kft	229	
134200					PSAP flow off
131932	134245	Profile 5	26.0 - 4.6 kft	231	
134304	134814	Profile 5	4.5 - 1.6 kft	228	1000 ft/min
134955	135424	restart Profile 5	1.6 - 0.1 kft	063	500 ft/min
135056					PSAP flow on
135453	135553	Profile 6	-.03 - 0.61 kft	068	
135602	140312	Run 9	0.64 - 0.60 kft	079	
140137					Heimann cal (10)
140325	142024	Profile 7	0.59 - 17.0 kft	091	
141800					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
142029	150643	Run 10	17.0 kft	090	
144500	(approx)				SATCOM call to NASA DC-8
150651	151632	Profile 8	17.0 - 7.0 kft	112	2000ft/min to 150825
151000	(approx)				HORACE crash
153230		Land	-.15 kft	267	
153924	GPS final	posn: 38 31.26N 28 42.98W			
153831	INU final	posn: 38 29.78N 28 42.51W			

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B032 Track 20-JUL-04

B032

SANTA MARIA RADIO	
NAT A	NAT E
3016	2962
5598	6628
8908	8821
13308	11301
17946	1794
VHF	
127.90	132.15
SELCAL	
① 426301	
① SATCOM Air-Com-1a1	

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11, panel 9/10

TYPES

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NAT TRACKS TO LISBON AIRPORT
NAT tracks are anchored on Espichel VORTAC and

RNAV required in all European upper
airspace. Should aircraft not be RNAV
equipped/nor operational, include a
"Negative-RNAV" report immediately
after the aircraft callsign on initial
contact on an ATC frequency.

ITOP – Interception and characterisation of N.American pollution

Mission Scientists: Claire Reeves and Paul Monks

Date: 20/7/04

Outline schedule:

06:00 - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

08:00 - Air Crew Briefing

09:15 – Clear aircraft

09:30 – Boarding deadline

10.00 - Take-off

Location: N and W of the Azores

Aim: To intercept air sampled by the DC8 on 18/07/04 in a flight heading NE from Pease, over Newfoundland out to 45W and 53N.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take off. Climb to first available level to perform a 5 minute run for wet chemistry check (10).
2. T+10 Profile climb at 1000ft/min to FL170 (5).
3. T+15 Straight and level run to ANAVA (39 54N, 25 24W) to include Noxy calcs (45).
4. T+60 Stepped profile ascent to FL240 at 1000ft/min to reach 41N. Interrupting profile for 5 minute runs at altitudes to be decided (probably 2). (20)
5. T+70 Stepped profile descent to FL140 at 1000ft/min due west. Interrupting profile for 5 minute runs at altitudes to be decided (probably 2). (20)
6. T+90 Repeat 4 and 5 along boundary of NOTAM (40).
7. T+130 Profile descent to 100ft at 500ft/min towards 40 30N, 34W (20).
8. T+150 Profile ascent to about 5000 ft at 500ft/min towards 40 30N, 34W (10).
9. T+160 Straight and level run on towards 40 30N, 34W for about 40 minutes to find centre of feature (40).
10. T+200 Profile descent to 1000 ft and perform a straight and level run for 10 minutes (15).
11. T+215 Ascend to 5000 ft at 500 ft/min and perform a straight and level run for 10 minutes (15).
12. T+230 Ascend to 7000 ft at 500 ft/min and perform a straight and level run for 10 minutes (15).
13. T+245 Profile ascend to FL260 at 1000ft/min on heading towards KOLIT (20).
14. T+265 Profile descent to 5000ft at 1000ft/min on heading towards KOLIT (15).
15. T+280 Transit to Horta at 5000ft including 20 minute straight and level run for NOxy calcs in clear air(60)
16. T+340 Search pattern over NNE of Pico if time allows. Land at Horta.

Ground power is required at Horta for one and half hours following flight.

B032 FWVS data

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...032

Date 20/7/04

Page 1 of

Log 00441234-75800

Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
V8		Lat	38° 31.26 N	←
No.		Long	28° 42.98 W	align <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Ends		Time	09 29 30	
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓ 4	SATCOM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
10:00:11		T/O						
10:10:00		Satcom to	Mr. Smith		re. filter operations			
10:17:01		F2170		73	-7.00	-22		
10:18:08		PSAP flow on						
10 34 05		J-W cal complete						
10 47 00		40° 03.75' N		25° 11.73' W	for EVM	"CO 600 pp6"		
		40° 03' 43" N		25° 11'				
11 10 00		Satcom - at		CCM	→ DFL			
11 27 00		Satcom - at call,		CCM/Amc Hubs	→ D. Oram			
11 31 27		start run 5						
11 39 25		TWC turned off,		trace looks unresponsive				
		tuned on						
11 40 30		TWC heater 2 turned on						
11 45 40								
11 50 09		start of profile 4 to F2170,		end of run 6 and				
		crash of HORACE						
11 56 42		profile 5						
12 00 30		end profile						
12 00 30		start of run 7						
12 47 30		end of 7						

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...032.....

Date20/7/04.....

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Video Tapes
V8
No.
Ends
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	40 29.58 N	40 27.10
Long	35 54.21 W	35 58.96
Time	13 34 30	13 35 40
Status	✓ 4	✓

DRS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
HORACE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SATCOM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
12 49 56		HORACE	crash					
13 05 00		HORACE	crash					
13 08 00		end of run						
13 09 34		profile ascent			41.55.16	N		
				14	34.06.48	U		
13 42 00		PSAP flow off						
13 50 56		PSAP flow on						
14 01 37		Heimann cal 10						
14 18 00		Satcom H	COM → DRZ					
		Received SATCOM call from NASA DC-8						
		DC8						
		011	871	552	62	22	12	
			0044	7753	88044			
		called DC-8	DC8 no =	00	871	552	622	212
15 06 51		Profile 8	2000	ft/min				
15 08 25			1000	ft/min		fl 145		
		HORACE	crash					
15 29 55		end run						
15 32 30		land						

QNH
Hdg
1021

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B032 20/7/04

Instruments

C.C-Att Inboard PC - locked up rebooted

HORACE crabs - 4

Aircraft